

ANALYSIS OF THE REQUIREMENTS APPLIED TO MEASURED INFORMATION WHEN CONDUCTING AN ENERGY AUDIT IN THE ENTERPRISE

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Annotatsiya: It is known that industrial enterprises are the main consumers of electricity. It is appropriate to start the first step in this direction with the creation of a database on the demand for electricity in industrial enterprises. The creation of a database describing the energy management of the enterprise in the main energy department of the enterprise and, on this basis, the creation of programs that allow obtaining analytical data on the energy consumption of the enterprise at all stages of the power supply system will determine the possibilities of energy saving. Of course, such an information system cannot replace the technical record system. However, it creates a system that provides use in all enterprises, is a thousand times cheaper, and allows to organize energy saving measures more efficiently.

Keywords: technological, sex, audit group, photo and thermogram of the transformer.

For energy saving measures, the energy auditor should receive more detailed information on the enterprise's electricity supply, electricity consumption graphs, the distribution of power flow to the point of entry, a complete list of technological and energy equipment. should be. Complete information on the manufactured product should be for the last year. Such information is obtained from the established information system and allows for more efficient organization of energy audits: the ability to quickly obtain energy use efficiency indicators for the current time; determine energy balances for all stages of the power supply system;

- the industrial enterprise must provide general information on all elements of the power supply system.

The creation of the database in electronic form creates such opportunities. For this, it should have the following components:

1. The industrial enterprise should have a database on electricity consumers of all elements of the power supply system and technological equipment.
2. To include a program for calculating energy use efficiency indicators for the current time.
3. The ability to read data by external programs and return the obtained results to the database.

The following requirements are set for electrical calculations of the database:

- calculations of energy consumption and wastage must be carried out strictly according to the stages of electricity supply;
- consumption and waste of electrical energy should be calculated according to the participation of electrical equipment in the technological process (main technological, auxiliary production, own needs, etc.) by separate stages of electricity supply;
- simultaneous release of the results of several options performed on the basis of the same conditions and formation of analytical data tables;
- use of programs that provide links between database tables.

The requirements defined above define the structure, components and calculation methodology of the database.

What information is needed by the head of the energy industry for the rational use of energy and resources:

- daily power demand graphs for each section or large consumer;
- information on energy consumption by groups of energy consumers (technological, auxiliary, communal-household, own needs);
- information on electricity quality indicators;
- general consumption graphs and energy indicators for the enterprise;
- technological, workshop and enterprise energy costs spent per unit of product;

- Analytical data and methodological instructions determining the efficiency of energy use.

Despite the fact that the introduction of such systems ensures high efficiency, such automated continuous control systems are still used in very few enterprises in our Republic. The main reason for this is that the implementation of such systems requires huge costs. Therefore, most enterprises do not have an information system that provides analytical data for energy saving measures

Figure 1. Members of the energy audit team and enterprise specialists conduct energy audits.

The following requirements are set for electrical calculations of the database:

-calculations of energy consumption and wastage must be carried out strictly according to the stages of electricity supply;

- consumption and waste of electrical energy should be calculated according to separate electricity supply heads according to the participation of electrical equipment in the technological process (main technological, auxiliary production, own needs, etc.);

- simultaneous release of the results of several options performed on the basis of the same conditions and formation of analytical data tables;

- use of programs that provide links between database tables.

The requirements defined above define the structure, components and calculation methodology of the database.

For the rational use of energy and resources, the head of the energy industry needs the following information:

- graphs of daily power consumption for each section or large consumer;
- information on energy consumption by groups of energy consumers (technological, auxiliary, communal-household, own needs);
- information on electricity quality indicators;
- general consumption graphs and energy indicators for the enterprise;
- technological, workshop and enterprise energy costs spent per unit of product;
- Analytical data and methodological instructions determining the efficiency of energy use.

Figure 14. Photo and thermogram of TM-1000/6.3 transformer at the enterprise.

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Adjustment processes continue continuously in high-tech equipment. Here, it is necessary to organize continuous monitoring and continuous measurement processes of technological process parameters. Particular importance is attached to

the measurement accuracy and reliability of these measuring instruments. The electronic driving system is also equipped with devices that continuously measure and control the driving parameters. Based on the indicators of these control elements, a control signal is generated for the electric drive. The peculiarity of these elements is that they change (analogously) according to continuously measured parameters. We will consider these elements separately.

Figure 15. Photo and thermogram of distribution equipment at the enterprise.

The production process of control-measuring devices studies the scientific principles and characteristics of control, protection and signaling systems, as well as the structure, characteristics and application of technical means-measuring devices used for their creation. This control is mainly carried out by means of electrical measuring devices. Automatic control is mainly carried out by converting non-electrical quantities into electrical signals. Therefore, apart from directly measuring devices, devices-sensors that convert non-electric quantities into electrical signals are also studied.

The goal of studying control-measuring instruments is the ability to introduce control-measuring elements that ensure the reliable operation of technological machines in optimal modes, high indicators of product quality, based on the wide development and improvement of the automation of production processes. to produce

According to the above, the main task of the topic is to explain measurement methods, the structure, schemes and characteristics of measuring instruments; It consists in teaching the principles and characteristics of operation, as well as helping them to gain knowledge about the industrial application of automatic control of production processes, automatic control of technological parameters, protection and signaling.

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